

Comparative effects of extracellular vesicles and liposomal nanocarriers on bleomycin-induced stress in A549 human adenocarcinoma cells

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ABSTRACT

Lung cancer and chronic respiratory diseases are among the leading causes of death worldwide. Key factors in their pathogenesis include reactive oxygen species (ROS), transforming growth factor- β 1 (TGF- β 1) and epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT). Exogenous antioxidants can mitigate the oxidative stress that drives TGF- β 1-mediated respiratory pathologies. Given their role in cellular communication and natural biocompatibility, extracellular vesicles (EVs) are emerging as promising candidates for the delivery of therapeutic cargo to pathological cells. Notably, microalgal-derived EVs (i.e., nanoalgosomes) have been shown to exhibit antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity. In this study, the bioactivity of EVs derived from *Tetraselmis chuii* (CCAP 66/21B) was investigated in a bleomycin-stressed ($8 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) human adenocarcinoma alveolar epithelial cell model (A549). Moreover, the effects of these EVs were compared to liposomes loaded with established therapeutics (pirfenidone and quercetin), synthesised using the lipid film hydration method. *In vitro* assessments included cell viability (MTS), intracellular ROS, morphological changes, cell migration, EMT-related mRNA expression (qPCR), and TGF- β 1 release (ELISA). Both the EVs (nanoalgosomes) and pirfenidone- and quercetin-loaded liposomal nanocarriers ($1\text{--}4 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) effectively attenuated bleomycin-induced EMT, inhibited cell migration, suppressed profibrotic TGF- β 1, lowered intracellular ROS and upregulated glutathione peroxidase 4 (GPX4). Importantly, the innate bioactive cargo of the naturally derived nanoalgosomes exhibited comparable effects to the liposome therapeutic formulations in mitigating bleomycin-induced stress in A549 cells.

1. Introduction

Oxidative stress in the airway epithelium triggers the infiltration and recruitment of inflammatory cells (e.g., neutrophils and macrophages) and the activation of proinflammatory cytokines such as transforming growth factor (TGF)- β 1 [6,12,20]. TGF- β 1 is a multifunctional cytokine that regulates cellular responses critical to tissue and immune homeostasis [12]. However, dysregulation of TGF- β 1 signaling is a key driver in the pathogenesis of fibrotic diseases such as idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis and cystic fibrosis, inflammatory diseases such as asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, and infectious diseases such as coronavirus disease [12,28,59]. TGF- β 1 also promotes tumor

progression or metastasis in the advanced stages of cancer [55]. This multi-faceted cytokine is the primary inducer of epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT), in which non-motile epithelial cell acquire an invasive mesenchymal phenotype [43,44]. In turn, EMT initiates extracellular matrix remodelling in inflammatory and tumor microenvironments [29]. As such, oxidative stress, excessive TGF- β 1 activation and EMT are central to the pathophysiological progression of chronic respiratory diseases and the initiating steps of the metastatic cascade [43,52]. The clinical development of new drugs is hindered by a failure rate exceeding 90 %, with more than half of these failures linked to poor efficacy and toxicity [46]. These challenges often arise not from the drugs themselves but from issues such as inadequate and uncontrolled

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delivery, rapid clearance, and difficulties in crossing cell membranes [46]. Encapsulation offers a promising solution by improving the pharmacokinetics and biodistribution of these therapies [14].

Extracellular vesicles (EVs) are natural nano-sized mediators of intercellular communication that contribute to maintaining cellular homeostasis [5]. EVs transport bioactives such as enzymes, metabolites and nucleic acids derived from their parent cell to recipient cells, and thereby modulate cellular processes [5]. The composition and bioactivity of this EV content is dependent on its parental cell type. For EV-based therapies, pre-clinical pharmacokinetics studies have suggested that the EV lipid bilayer enhances the biodistribution of exogenous EVs and protects its bioactive cargo for enhanced therapeutic delivery [13]. As such, EVs are recognized both for their intrinsic therapeutic effects and considered promising biological vectors for active compounds. Recent studies have shown that EVs from microalgae (i.e., nanoalgsomes) exhibit biocompatibility both *in vitro*, using various human cell lines, and *in vivo*, following a single intravenous dose in mouse models [2]. Moreover, nanoalgsomes can be internalized by cells through clathrin-mediated endocytosis and localize within the endosomal compartment after uptake [2,38]. Furthermore, nanoalgsomes derived from the chlorophyte *Tetraselmis chuii* have been shown to reduce oxidative stress and modulate the expression of oxidative stress-responsive genes in both tumoral (MDA-MB231) and normal (1–7 HB2) cell lines, as well as *in vivo*, in a *Caenorhabditis elegans* model [2]. These nanoalgsomes have also been shown to reduce the production of proinflammatory cytokines, such as interleukin-6 (IL-6), in lipopolysaccharide-activated THP-1 cells [2].

The current study further investigates the bioactive properties of nanoalgsomes and evaluates their potential as EV-based effectors in pulmonary pharmacology. Specifically, this work examines the capacity of nanoalgsomes to attenuate bleomycin-induced stress in lung carcinoma epithelial cells (A549). Bleomycin-induced stress in A549 cells is a well-established model for pulmonary fibrosis and chemotherapy-induced lung injury, enabling the study of oxidative stress, inflammation, and fibrotic processes relevant to both lung disease and cancer progression [9,40,48]. Moreover, the innate bioactivity of these natural nanoalgsomes is compared to that of liposomes loaded with the established therapeutics pirfenidone and quercetin. For context, pirfenidone is one of two drugs currently approved for the treatment of idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis and has been shown to suppress lung metastasis [57]. Quercetin is a polyphenolic flavonoid that alleviates bleomycin-mediated fibrosis and EMT by acting on the SIRT1/AMPK signaling pathway [25]. Liposomal nanovehicles are capable of encapsulating hydrophilic and difficult-to-deliver hydrophobic drugs, and can thereby improve the pharmacokinetics, solubility and biodistribution of their bioactive cargo [3]. Previous studies have demonstrated that liposomal loading significantly improves the bioavailability, cellular uptake and bioactivity of both pirfenidone and quercetin [17,32,42].

Nanoalgsomes, as naturally occurring EVs, may offer bioactive properties (such as anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects) that liposomes, as synthetic carriers, cannot provide. In this context, the present study aims to directly compare naturally-derived nanoalgsomes, isolated from the microalgae *T. chuii* using a scalable process, to synthetic liposomes loaded with pirfenidone and quercetin. The study evaluates whether the natural composition of nanoalgsomes effectively modulates oxidative stress and fibrosis-related pathways, similar to the loaded-liposome formulations. Thus, this work aims to enhance understanding of the unique bioactive potential of nanoalgsomes in attenuating oxidative stress, fibrosis, and related metabolic alterations in pulmonary diseases and cancer.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Tetraselmis chuii (CCAP 66/21B) was obtained from the Culture

Collection of Algae and Protozoa (Scotland). 1,2-dioleoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphoethanolamine (DOPE, purity $\geq 99\%$), L- α -phosphatidylcholine (egg PC, purity $\geq 99\%$) and cholesterol (Chol, purity $\geq 99\%$) were acquired from Merck (Germany). Phosphate buffered saline (DPBS-buffer, $-\text{Mg}^{2+}$, $-\text{Ca}^{2+}$), 1,1'-Dioctadecyl-3,3',3'-tetramethylindocarbocyanine perchlorate (DiI) and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, purity $> 99\%$) were procured from Merck (Germany). Ethanol (99.5%) was purchased from Carl Roth (Germany). Pirfenidone (Acros Organics), quercetin dihydrate (97%) (Alfa Aesar) and Ham's F-12 nutrient mix medium were obtained from Fisher Scientific (USA). Fetal bovine serum (FBS) was obtained from Cytiva (Austria) and trypan blue solution from VWR International (USA). The MTS assay was procured from Promega (UK). The fluorometric Intracellular ROS kit, human TGF- β 1 ELISA kit, bleomycin sulphate and penicillin-streptomycin were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany). The QuantiTect Reverse Transcription Kit and QuantiNova™ SYBR Green PCR Kit were acquired from Qiagen (Germany).

2.2. Microalgal cultivation and nanoalgsome isolation via tangential flow filtration

Tetraselmis chuii (CCAP 66/21B) was cultivated in a sterile 10 L borosilicate glass photobioreactor under continuous 0.22 μm -filtered air flow ($Q \sim 0.65 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$). Following a 10% v/v inoculum in f/2 (-Si) medium, *T. chuii* (5 L, 1 mg wet biomass mL^{-1}) was incubated at $15 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ using a light intensity of 80 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ with light:dark cycles of 14:10 h for a 28-day batch cultivation regime. The cell growth was monitored weekly by absorbance measurements at $\lambda = 600 \text{ nm}$ using a FLUOstar OMEGA microplate reader (BMG labtech, Ortenberg, Germany). At day 28 of cultivation, nanoalgsome isolation was conducted using the Repligen KrosFlo KR2i TFF System (Spectrum Labs., Los Angeles, CA, United States) as described by Adamo et al. [1] and Picciotto et al. [38] with minor modifications. As such, microfiltration and ultrafiltration parameters are summarised in Table 1 with a schematic diagram of the process being provided in Fig. 1. Following diafiltration with DPBS, nanoalgsome samples were stored at -20°C until further analysis.

2.3. Liposome synthesis and purification

2.3.1. Liposome synthesis

Liposomes were prepared using the lipid film hydration method incorporating cholesterol (Chol), L- α -phosphatidylcholine (egg PC) and 1,2-dioleoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphoethanolamine (DOPE) (molar ratio 1:1:1) [16]. As such, 2 mL of chloroform, 398 μL of 10 mg Chol mL^{-1} , 334 μL of 25 mg egg PC mL^{-1} , 767 μL of 10 mg DOPE mL^{-1} and 1.15 μL of 26 mM 1,1'-Dioctadecyl-3,3',3'-tetramethylindocarbocyanine perchlorate were added to a 50 mL round-bottom flask. The mixture was evaporated at 350 mbar for 30 min and then at 3 mbar for 60 min at 42°C using a Heidolph Laborata 4000 rotary evaporator (Heidolph, Schwabach, Germany) equipped with a Vacuubrand PC2001 pump (Wertheim, Schwabach, Germany). The lipid film was hydrated with 4 mL of DPBS, stirred at 300 rpm for 30 min at ambient temperature and then sonicated for 20 min to form multilamellar vesicles. The formulation was then sequentially extruded through polycarbonate membranes of reducing pore sizes (800 nm, 400 nm, 200 nm and 100 nm) to produce small unilamellar vesicles and stored at 4°C until further use. Loaded liposome formulations were prepared by modification of the aforementioned procedure as follows: (a) rehydration of the lipid film with pirfenidone (2 mg mL^{-1}) in DPBS for pirfenidone-loaded liposomes, (b) the addition of 1030 μL quercetin dihydrate (1 mg mL^{-1}) to the lipid mixture prior to evaporation for quercetin-loaded liposomes (10% quercetin dihydrate to lipid molar ratio) and (c) the addition of 1030 μL quercetin dihydrate (1 mg mL^{-1}) to the lipid mixture prior to evaporation with subsequent rehydration of the quercetin-containing lipid film with pirfenidone (2 mg mL^{-1}) in DPBS for pirfenidone and quercetin

Table 1

Sequential fractionation via tangential flow filtration for nanoalgosome isolation (<200 nm nanoalgosome >500 kDa).

Sequential TFF Steps	Hollow Fiber Cartridge Model	Pore size Cut-off	Feed flow rate Inlet Q	Permeate flow Filtrate Q	Transmembrane Pressure (TMP)
1. Microfiltration Clarification	MiniKros S04-E65U-07-N	650 nm	1000 mL min ⁻¹	< 500 mL min ⁻¹	< 0.16
2. Microfiltration Isolation	MiniKros S04-P20U-05-N	200 nm	1000 mL min ⁻¹	< 500 mL min ⁻¹	< 0.17
3. Ultrafiltration Concentration	MiniKros S04-E500-05-N	500 kDa	1000 mL min ⁻¹	< 350 mL min ⁻¹	< 0.24
4. Ultrafiltration Diafiltration	MicroKros C02-E500-05-N	500 kDa	80 mL min ⁻¹	< 10 mL min ⁻¹	< 0.25

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of nanoalgosome biosynthesis and isolation by tangential flow filtration (<200 nm nanoalgosome >500 kDa). The microalgal culture was clarified using a 650 nm filter. Then, nanoalgosomes were isolated using a 200 nm filter. This fraction was then subjected to concentration and diafiltration using a 500 kDa filter.

co-loaded liposomes.

2.3.2. Liposome purification and evaluation of drug-encapsulation

Centrifugal ultrafiltration was used to differentiate between free (non-entrapped) and liposome-associated (encapsulated) content [30]. Amicon ultra centrifugal filters (Millipore, 100 kDa MWCO) were washed with DPBS prior to use. Liposome formulations (500 μ L) were subjected to four cycles of 6000 \times g centrifugal ultrafiltration for 60 min at ambient temperature (Eppendorf Centrifuge 5424, Hamburg, Germany). After each ultrafiltration cycle, the retentate and permeate volumes were measured and analysed by UV-vis spectrophotometry (Tecan Infinite M1000, Männedorf, Switzerland) to evaluate the content distribution (μ g) of pirfenidone ($\lambda_{\max} = 310$ nm, $n = 14$, 5–100 μ g mL⁻¹, $R^2 = 0.9988$, $y = 0.0071x$) and quercetin ($\lambda_{\max} = 372$ nm, $n = 14$, 5–100 μ g mL⁻¹, $R^2 = 0.9999$, $y = 0.0169x$). The retentate was then diluted to the initial volume (500 μ L) with DPBS and subjected to the next round of centrifugation. Blank liposomes spiked with free pirfenidone and quercetin were also subjected to centrifugal ultrafiltration as controls. Free drug (i.e. cumulative content loss), liposome-associated content and encapsulation efficiency (EE) were determined as follows:

- Content loss (%) = [Non-encapsulated content removed by ultrafiltration cycle (μ g) / Content in the liposome formulation prior to ultrafiltration (μ g)] \times 100.
- Liposome-associated content (%) = 100 % - cumulative content loss by ultrafiltration cycles (%)

- Encapsulation efficiency (%) = [Content in the final retentate (μ g) i.e. purified liposomes / Initial quantity added to the liposome formulation (μ g)] \times 100.

2.4. Nanoalgosome and liposome characterisation

2.4.1. BCA protein assay

Nanoalgosome protein content was quantified using a BCA Protein Assay Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Absorbance was measured at $\lambda = 562$ nm using a GloMax Discover Microplate Reader. A bovine serum albumin (BSA) standard curve was used for BSA-equivalent quantification.

2.4.2. Nanoparticle Tracking Analysis (NTA)

Nanoalgosome size distribution and concentration were measured according to Adamo et al. [1] using a NanoSight NS300 (Malvern Panalytical, UK) equipped with a 488 nm laser and cCMOS camera. Nanoalgosome samples were diluted with particle-free water to obtain 20–120 particles per frame and the recommended concentration range (10^8 – 10^9 particles per mL). Each sample was analysed 5 times for 60 s for a total of 1500 frames by NTA 3.4 Build 3.4.003 (camera level 15–16).

2.4.3. Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS)

The hydrodynamic diameter and polydispersity index (PDI) of diluted dispersions (20 μ L sample in 180 μ L DPBS) were measured with a Zetasizer Nano S90 (Malvern Panalytical GmbH, Germany) at 20 °C. Z-average values were calculated as averages and deviations of the main peaks of three technical replicates.

2.4.4. Zeta potential

For zeta-potential (ζ -potential) characterization, surface charge measurements were conducted using a Zetasizer Nano Z (Malvern Panalytical GmbH, Germany). Diluted dispersions (30 μL sample in 770 μL of 100 mM potassium chloride, KCl, solution) were loaded into disposable folded capillary cells and measurements were performed at 25 °C after 2 min equilibration. Zeta potential values were calculated as averages and deviations of the main peaks of three technical replicates.

2.4.5. Transmission Electron Cryomicroscopy (Cryo-TEM)

For cryo-TEM examination, the samples were vitrified using a Vitrobot Mark V plunging device (Thermo Fisher, Hillsboro, Oregon). Sample dispersions (3 μL) were then applied to a Quantifoil or Lacey carbon coated TEM grid that had been glow discharged using an oxygen plasma cleaner (Diener Nano, Diener electronic, Germany). After removing excess sample solution with filter paper, the grid was immediately plunged into liquid ethane. The specimen was transferred to a TEM (FEI Titan Krios G4) maintaining cryogenic conditions for subsequent examination. Conventional TEM imaging was achieved using an acceleration voltage of 300 kV and micrographs were acquired with a 4k Direct Electron Detection Camera (Gatan K3) under low dose conditions.

2.5. Human alveolar epithelial cell culture

2.5.1. Cell culture and treatments

Human alveolar epithelial cells (A549) were cultured in Ham's F12 medium supplemented with 10 % v/v fetal bovine serum (FBS) and 1 % w/v penicillin-streptomycin at 37 °C, 5 % CO₂. A549 cells were sub-cultured twice weekly with exponential phase cells used in all experiments. Cell viability and counts were determined by the trypan blue exclusion assay as described in Cooper et al. [10]. For experiments, A549 cells were incubated for 24 h at 37 °C, 5 % CO₂. The medium was then removed and the cells were washed with DPBS three times prior to the addition of serum-free medium. The fibrotic agent (bleomycin sulphate, Apollo Scientific) and treatments (EVs or liposomes) were then individually or collectively administered to the A549 cell line for 24 h. For collective treatments, a 4-hour pre-treatment was administered using either nanoaliosomes or loaded-liposomes, with the following concentrations: 1–4 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of EV protein for nanoaliosomes, 1–4 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of loaded pirfenidone, 0.25–1 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of loaded quercetin, or 1–4 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of pirfenidone and 0.06–0.24 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of quercetin for co-loaded liposomes. After the pre-treatment, the fibrotic agent (8 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) was added, for a total cumulative treatment duration of 24 h. Empty liposomes, DPBS and non-treated cells were included as the vehicle and negative controls, respectively. Cell culture experiments were performed with three independent biological samples, each consisting of three technical replicates.

2.5.2. Cell viability

Cells were seeded at a density of 5×10^4 cells mL^{-1} . Following 24 h treatments in serum-free media, cell viability was assessed using the Promega CellTiter 96 Aqueous One Solution Cell Proliferation (MTS) assay according to the manufacturer's instructions. Absorbance was measured at $\lambda = 490$ nm (FLUOstar OPTIMA, BMG Labtech, Ortenberg, Germany). Absorbance values were adjusted to compensate for the background contribution and normalised to the DPBS or empty liposome vehicle control. Viability (percent of control) was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Viability (\%)} = \left[\frac{\text{Experimental viability}}{\text{Negative control viability}} \right] \times 100.$$

Values were expressed as mean \pm SD of three independent experiments.

2.6. Intracellular reactive oxygen species

Intracellular ROS was assessed using a fluorometric intracellular ROS kit (MAK143, Sigma-Aldrich) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Cells were seeded in 96-well plates at a density of 5×10^4 cells mL^{-1} . Following 24 h treatments in serum-free media and washing steps, 100 μL of master reaction mix was added to the wells and the cells were incubated for 1 h at 37 °C. Fluorescence was measured by fluorescence spectroscopy at an excitation and emission wavelength of 490 nm/520 nm, respectively (FLUOstar OPTIMA, BMG Labtech, Ortenberg, Germany). Fluorescence values were adjusted to compensate for the background contribution and normalised to the DPBS vehicle control.

Intracellular ROS (fold change relative to control) was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Intracellular ROS} = \left[\frac{\text{Experimental ROS}}{\text{Negative control ROS}} \right]$$

Values were expressed as mean \pm SD of three independent experiments.

2.7. Cell migration and morphological observation

Cells were seeded at a density of 5×10^5 cells mL^{-1} and exposed to treatments accordingly. For migration analysis, confluent cells were scratched with sterile 200 μL micropipette tips. Following PBS washing steps, treatments were applied accordingly in serum-free media. Images were acquired using a VWR VisiScope IT404 microscope equipped with a AmScope MD500 camera at 0 and 24 h. Image J software was used to quantify migration (fold change relative to control) as follows:

$$\text{Migration} = \left[\frac{\text{Mean gap area at 0 h} - \text{Mean gap area at 24 h}}{\text{Mean gap area at 0 h for negative control} - \text{Mean gap area at 24 h for negative control}} \right]$$

Values were expressed as mean \pm SD of three independent experiments.

2.7.1. EMT-related mRNA expression (RT-qPCR)

Cells (3×10^5 cells mL^{-1}) were incubated for 24 h at 37 °C, 5 % CO₂. The cells were then exposed to treatments in serum-free media for 24 h. Following treatments, RNA was isolated using Invitrogen TRIzol reagent according to the manufacturer's instructions. Specifically, the medium was removed and 400 μL of TRIzol reagent was added to each well prior to 5 min incubation at ambient temperature. Then, 80 μL of chloroform was added to facilitate phase separation. This mixture was shaken to form an emulsion and incubated for 3 min at ambient temperature. Following centrifugation at 12,000 $\times g$ for 15 min at 4 °C (Hettich Mikro 200 R), the aqueous phase containing the RNA was collected. For precipitation of the RNA, 200 μL of ice cold isopropanol was added and incubated for 10 min at ambient temperature. Following centrifugation at 12,000 $\times g$ for 10 min at 4 °C, the supernatant was discarded and the RNA pellet was washed with 400 μL of 75 % v/v ethanol. The RNA pellet was then centrifuged at 7500 $\times g$ for 5 min at 4 °C, after which the supernatant was discarded. The RNA pellet was air-dried prior to resuspension with 20 μL of RNase-free water. RNA quality and concentration were determined using a DeNovix DS-11 spectrophotometer. A 260 nm/280 nm ratio of 1.8–2.0 was considered indicative of high RNA purity. Then, cDNA was synthesised from 800 ng of RNA using the QuantiTect Reverse Transcription Kit (Qiagen) and subsequently amplified using the QuantiNova SYBR Green PCR Kit (Qiagen) according to the manufacturer's instructions (Qiagen). PCR was conducted on the StepOnePlus Real-Time PCR System (Applied Biosystem). PCR cycles were as follows: Holding stage (95 °C for 10 min), cycling stage (35 cycles: step 1, 95 °C for 15 s; step 2, 60 °C for 1 min), and melt curve stage (step 1, 95 °C for 15 s; step 2, 60 °C for 1 min; step 3, 95 °C for 15 s). Relative expression

was estimated using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct}$ method. Values were expressed as mean \pm SD of three independent reactions.

Table 2 shows the gene targets for EMT-related mRNA expression. Transforming growth factor beta-1 (TGF- β 1) plays a central role in EMT [43]. Epithelial cadherin (*CDH1*) is found within the membrane of epithelial cells [35]. Vimentin (*VIM*) is found in mesenchymal cells [36]. *CDH1* and *VIM* are markers for epithelial to mesenchymal transition. Upregulation of Fibronectin (*FNI*) and the decreased expression of glutathione peroxidase 4 (*GPX4*) are hallmarks of tumour progression and fibrotic conditions [37,47,54].

2.7.2. ELISA for human transforming growth factor beta 1

Cells (5×10^4 cells mL $^{-1}$) were incubated for 24 h at 37 °C, 5 % CO $_2$. The cells were then exposed to treatments in serum-free media for 24 h. The release of TGF- β 1 into conditioned media was quantified using the human TGF- β 1 ELISA kit (RAB0460, Sigma-Aldrich) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Specifically, following TGF- β 1 sample activation, 100 μ L of conditioned media was added to wells coated with anti-human TGF- β 1. The plate was then incubated for 2.5 h at ambient temperature prior to washing and a 100 μ L addition of biotinylated human TGF- β 1 detection antibody. After 1 h incubation at ambient temperature and washing steps, 100 μ L of horseradish peroxidase (HRP)-Streptavidin was added and the plate was incubated for 45 min at ambient temperature. Following washing steps, 100 μ L of the ELISA Colorimetric TMB Reagent (3,3',5,5'-Tetramethylbenzidine, HRP Substrate) was added. The plate was incubated in the dark for 30 min at ambient temperature prior to the addition of the ELISA Stop Solution and an immediate absorbance measurement at $\lambda = 450$ nm (FLUOstar OMEGA microplate reader, BMG labtech, Ortenberg, Germany). TGF- β 1 was quantified using a calibration curve of human TGF- β 1 protein standard ($n = 7$, 16.38 pg mL $^{-1}$ to 400 pg mL $^{-1}$, $R^2 = 0.991$, $y = 0.060x^{0.257}$). Samples and standards were tested in triplicate.

2.8. Statistical analysis

The Kruskal-Wallis test with pairwise comparisons (using a significance threshold of $p = 0.05$) was performed to assess significant differences between cell culture treatments in terms of viability, intracellular ROS, migration, TGF- β 1 release, and EMT-related mRNA expression. All statistical analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics version 29 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA).

3. Results

3.1. Loaded-liposome synthesis, purification and absorbance spectra of free drugs and liposome formulations

Liposomes were successfully prepared using the lipid film hydration method, incorporating cholesterol, egg phosphatidylcholine, and DOPE in a 1:1:1 molar ratio. The resulting lipid films were hydrated, stirred, sonicated, and sequentially extruded through polycarbonate membranes to form small unilamellar vesicles. Two loading strategies were used based on the different solubility properties of pirfenidone and quercetin. Pirfenidone was incorporated into the rehydration buffer [24]. However, quercetin was incorporated into the lipid-film prior to rehydration [15]. Following sonication and extrusion steps, the liposomal formulations were then purified by centrifugal ultrafiltration to remove the unencapsulated free drug [30]. For co-loading, quercetin was first incorporated into the lipid-film prior to rehydration with the pirfenidone-containing buffer (Fig. 2).

Fig. 3 (A) and (B) show the purification of the loaded liposomal formulations by centrifugal ultrafiltration and the removal of unencapsulated drug compared to free drug samples spiked with empty liposomes. As such, 4 cycles at 6000 \times g for 60 min at ambient temperature using 100 kDa Amicon ultra centrifugal filters was sufficient to remove unencapsulated drug from the loaded liposomal formulations. Fig. 3 (C) shows the absorbance spectra for pirfenidone ($\lambda_{max} = 310$ nm) and quercetin ($\lambda_{max} = 372$ nm). Fig. 3 (D) shows the absorbance spectra for the final loaded and purified liposomes adjusted to account for the background spectrum of empty liposomes. With the loading strategies utilised, encapsulation efficiency (EE) was 5.5 % for pirfenidone liposomes and 5.1 % for quercetin liposomes. The co-loaded formulation encapsulated 328.0 ± 4.3 μ g pirfenidone and 19.6 ± 1.3 μ g quercetin i.e., 1.00:0.06 pirfenidone to quercetin ratio (EE: 4.1 % and 1.9 % respectively).

3.2. Nanoalgosome and liposome characterisation

Nanoalgosomes were isolated from *Tetraselmis chuii* (CCAP 66/21B) conditioned-media. In line with previous studies [1,2,38], the nanoalgosomes were characterized using several biophysical techniques, demonstrating low batch-to-batch variability and a ratio of 1 μ g of total nanoalgosome protein (measured by BCA) corresponding to 10^{10} particles (measured by NTA). Examined by DLS, the nanoalgosomes were smaller and had a greater polydispersity index than the liposomes (Table 3). Zeta potential measurements ranged from -22 ± 1 mV (nanoalgosomes) to -45 ± 2 mV (empty liposomes). An increase in zeta potential was observed for loaded liposome formulations compared to

Table 2

Primer sequences for EMT-related mRNA expression. The results were normalised to the endogenous control gene *GADPH*.

Gene Name and Ascension Number	Primer Forward Sequence (5'-3')	Primer Reverse Sequence (5'-3')
<i>GAPDH</i> ^a NM_002046	GTCTCCTCTGACTTCAACAGCG	ACCACCCTGTGTCTGTAGCCAA
TGF Beta 1 (<i>TGF-β1</i>) ^b NM_000660	TACCTGAACCGGTGTGCTCTC	GTTGCTGAGGTATGCCAGGAA
E Cadherin (<i>CDH1</i>) ^a NM_004360	GCCTCCTGAAAGAGAGTGGAAAG	TGGCAGTGTCTCTCAAATCCG
Vimentin (<i>VIM</i>) ^a NM_003380	AGGCAAAGCAGGAGTCCACTGA	ATCTGGCGTCCAGGGACTCAT
Fibronectin (<i>FNI</i>) ^a NM_212482	ACAACACCGAGGTGACTGAGAC	GGACACAACGATGTTCTCTGAG
Glutathione peroxidase 4 (<i>GPX4</i>) ^c NM_002085	ACAAGAACGGCTGCGTGGTGAA	GCCACACACTTGTGGAGCTAGA

References

- ^a [19];
^b [22];
^c [18].

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of liposomal formulation and purification.

Fig. 3. The effect of ultrafiltration cycles on (A) pirfenidone content (%) and (B) quercetin content (%) for liposome formulations and free drug controls spiked with empty liposomes subjected to ultrafiltration ($6000 \times g$, 60 min at ambient temperature). Dashed lines are used as visual guides to assist the reader in following trends in the data. (C) Absorbance spectra for pirfenidone ($\lambda_{max} = 310$ nm) and quercetin ($\lambda_{max} = 372$ nm) standards. (D) Absorbance spectra for pirfenidone-loaded, quercetin-loaded and pirfenidone and quercetin co-loaded liposomes adjusted to account for the background spectrum of empty liposomes.

the empty liposomes (Table 3). Observed by cryo-TEM, Fig. 4 (A) shows that all liposome samples contained a combination of both multilamellar and unilamellar vesicles. Furthermore, Fig. 4 (B) shows that the loaded liposomes exhibited a larger hydrodynamic size compared to the empty liposomes.

3.3. The effects of the fibrotic agent (Bleomycin Sulphate) on the human adenocarcinoma alveolar epithelial cell model (A549)

Bleomycin-induced stress in A549 cells is a well-established model for epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition, oxidative stress, elevated TGF-

Table 3

Z-average (D_h , nm), polydispersity index (PDI) and zeta potential (mV) for the nanoparticles.

Nanoparticle	Z-average (nm)	Polydispersity index	Zeta potential (mV)
Nanoalgaesome	85 ± 1	0.28 ± 0.01	-22 ± 1
Empty liposome	127 ± 2	0.10 ± 0.01	-45 ± 2
Pirfenidone liposome	149 ± 3	0.14 ± 0.03	-38 ± 3
Quercetin liposome	163 ± 2	0.12 ± 0.01	-34 ± 1
Pirfenidone and quercetin co-loaded liposome	158 ± 5	0.12 ± 0.01	-36 ± 1

β 1 and fibrotic processes relevant to both lung disease and cancer progression [9,40,48]. Fig. 5 (A) shows that bleomycin treatment induced a morphological shift in A549 cells from an epithelial to a mesenchymal phenotype, characterized by elongation and the development of a fusiform, spindle-like morphology [23]. Fig. 5 (B) shows a significant cytotoxic effect of bleomycin ($>16 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) on A549 cells ($p = 0.002$). In Fig. 5 (C), the scratch assay reveals that bleomycin treatment ($>8 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) significantly promoted cell migration and gap closure ($p = 0.018$). Furthermore, Fig. 5 (D) illustrates a significant increase in intracellular ROS levels ($p = 0.004$), while Fig. 5 (E) demonstrates a significant accumulation of TGF- β 1 measured by ELISA, a key regulator of epithelial-mesenchymal transition ($p = 0.022$). For collective treatments, $8 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of bleomycin sulphate was administered to induce stress as this concentration had no significant effect on viability, yet significantly increased migration, intracellular ROS and TGF- β 1.

3.4. The effects of the nanoalgaesomes and loaded liposomes on the human adenocarcinoma alveolar epithelial cell model (A549) exposed to the fibrotic agent

Dose-response curves were generated for all treatments to identify the concentrations at which nanoalgaesomes, pirfenidone- and quercetin-liposomes were effective in modulating migration, oxidative stress, epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT), and TGF- β 1 accumulation, while minimizing cytotoxicity. Concentrations were selected based on the dose-response data and previous studies [2,4,41], which reported effective ranges for A549 cells and other lung cell lines. The selected concentrations ($0.25\text{--}1 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for quercetin and $1\text{--}4 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for pirfenidone and nanoalgaesomes) did not significantly affect cell viability (Appendices Figure A4). These concentrations were optimized to ensure minimal toxicity while achieving the desired biological effects.

3.4.1. Intracellular ROS attenuation

Elevated reactive oxygen species (ROS) play a central role in the progression of chronic airway inflammation and the pathogenesis of inflammatory lung disease [8]. Fig. 6 illustrates the attenuation of intracellular ROS, highlighting the antioxidant properties of the nanoalgaesomes and loaded liposomes. A 4-hour pre-treatment with these nanocarriers was administered prior to the addition of the bleomycin fibrotic agent, resulting in a cumulative 24-hour treatment period. Both the nanoalgaesomes and loaded liposomes significantly reduced intracellular ROS levels in a dose-dependant manner compared to the bleomycin-only treatment group ($0 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of nanoalgaesomes or loaded liposomes). The statistical analysis using the Kruskal-Wallis test

Fig. 4. (A) Cryo-TEM images of (1) nanoalgaesomes, (2) pirfenidone liposomes, (3) quercetin liposomes and (4) pirfenidone and quercetin co-loaded liposomes. Representative of three independent experimental images. Scale bar: 50 nm. (B) Hydrodynamic size distribution of nanoalgaesomes, empty liposomes, pirfenidone-loaded, quercetin-loaded and pirfenidone and quercetin co-loaded liposomes, as measured by DLS. Data represent averages from three technical replicates.

Fig. 5. The effects of bleomycin sulphate (24 h treatment) on A549 (A) morphology and migration. Representative of three independent experimental images. Scale bar: 50 μm . (B) cell viability (percent of negative control, 0 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$). (C) cell migration (fold change relative to negative control, 0 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$). (D) intracellular ROS (fold change relative to negative control, 0 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$). (E) TGF- β 1 (pg mL^{-1}). Data are presented as means \pm S.D. ($n = 3$ independent biological samples). Statistical significance compared to the negative control was assessed using the Kruskal-Wallis test with post-hoc pairwise comparisons: ns (not significant, $p > 0.05$), * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$ and *** $p \leq 0.001$.

showed significant results for nanoalgsomes ($p = 0.011$), pirfenidone liposomes ($p = 0.011$), quercetin liposomes ($p = 0.013$) and pirfenidone and quercetin co-loaded liposomes ($p = 0.009$).

3.4.2. Migration attenuation

Cell migration is a hallmark of bleomycin-induced stress [40]. Cells undergoing epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) have a greater potential for migration and invasive properties [36]. Observed using the scratch assay, bleomycin treatment stimulated A549 cell migration and

Fig. 6. The effects of (A) nanoalgosomes, (B) pirfenidone liposomes, (C) quercetin liposomes and (D) pirfenidone and quercetin co-loaded liposomes on intracellular ROS in A549 cells exposed to the fibrotic agent, 8 µg mL⁻¹ bleomycin sulphate (fold change relative to negative control). All data are presented as means ± S.D. (n = 3 independent biological samples). Statistical significance compared to the negative control was assessed using the Kruskal-Wallis test with post-hoc pairwise comparisons: ns (not significant) $p > 0.05$, * $p \leq 0.05$ and *** $p \leq 0.001$.

more pronounced gap closure compared to the negative control. Fig. 7 shows that the treatments (nanoalgosomes and loaded liposomes) significantly attenuated cell migration in a dose-dependant manner in the bleomycin-stressed cell model, compared to the bleomycin-exclusive group (0 µg mL⁻¹ of nanoalgosomes or loaded liposomes). The statistical analysis using the Kruskal-Wallis test showed significant results for nanoalgosomes ($p = 0.003$), pirfenidone liposomes ($p = 0.044$), quercetin liposomes ($p = 0.017$) and pirfenidone and quercetin co-loaded liposomes ($p = 0.01$).

3.4.3. TGF beta 1 (TGF-β1) Expression

The TGF-β1 gene provides instructions for producing a protein called transforming growth factor beta-1 (TGF-β1), which plays a central role in inducing epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) [43]. Fig. 8 shows that the treatments (nanoalgosomes and loaded liposomes) significantly decreased TGF-β1 mRNA expression compared to the bleomycin-only treatment group (0 µg mL⁻¹ of nanoalgosomes or loaded liposomes). The statistical analysis using the Kruskal-Wallis test showed significant results for nanoalgosomes ($p = 0.013$), pirfenidone liposomes ($p =$

0.017), quercetin liposomes ($p = 0.024$) and pirfenidone and quercetin co-loaded liposomes ($p = 0.019$).

3.4.4. Epithelial cadherin (CDH1) expression

The CDH1 gene encodes epithelial cadherin, a protein found in the membranes of epithelial cells that plays a critical role in cell adhesion and the formation of organized tissues [34,35]. E-cadherin also functions as a tumor suppressor by preventing uncontrolled cell growth and division. Fig. 9 shows that the treatments (nanoalgosomes and loaded liposomes) significantly increased CDH1 mRNA expression ($p \leq 0.05$) compared to the bleomycin-only treatment group (0 µg mL⁻¹ of nanoalgosomes or loaded liposomes). Additionally, VIMm RNA expression was examined (Appendices Figure A5). The VIM gene encodes vimentin, a cytoskeletal protein predominantly found in mesenchymal cells. The Kruskal-Wallis test revealed statistical differences between the bleomycin-only treatment groups and the negative control in each case ($p \leq 0.05$). However, the treatments (nanoalgosomes and loaded liposomes) restored VIM mRNA expression to levels similar to the negative control. This data suggests that the treatments (nanoalgosomes and

Fig. 7. The effects of (A) nanoalgosomes (B) pirfenidone liposomes, (C) quercetin liposomes and (D) pirfenidone and quercetin co-loaded liposomes on the migration of A549 cells exposed to the fibrotic agent, $8 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ bleomycin sulphate (fold change relative to negative control). All data are presented as means \pm S.D. ($n = 3$ independent biological samples). Statistical significance compared to the negative control was assessed using the Kruskal-Wallis test with post-hoc pairwise comparisons: ns (not significant) $p > 0.05$, * $p \leq 0.05$ and ** $p \leq 0.01$.

loaded liposomes) act as effectors in EMT.

3.4.5. Fibronectin (FN1) and glutathione peroxidase 4 (GPX4) expression and TGF- β 1 quantification

Excessive accumulation of the extracellular matrix protein fibronectin is a characteristic of tumor progression, fibrosis, and other pathological conditions [47,54]. Additionally, glutathione peroxidase 4 (GPX4) plays a key role in regulating TGF- β -induced myofibroblast differentiation by modulating reactive oxygen species (ROS) and Smad signaling in lung fibroblasts [49]. As such, Fig. 10 (A) shows that the treatments significantly reduced fibronectin (FN1) mRNA expression ($p = 0.24$) and increased GPX4 expression ($p \leq 0.05$) compared to the bleomycin-only treatment group. Furthermore, TGF- β 1 plays a central role in inducing EMT [43]. In Fig. 10 (B), quantification of TGF- β 1 by ELISA reveals that the treatments significantly reduced the accumulation of TGF- β 1 compared to the bleomycin-exclusive treatment group ($p = 0.011$).

4. Discussion

Chronic respiratory diseases and lung cancer are among the leading

causes of death worldwide [53]. As such, novel therapeutics are required for to improve patient outcomes and provide treatment options other than palliative care. The present study examined the capacity of biogenic extracellular vesicles (nanoalgosomes), to alleviate bleomycin-induced stress in lung carcinoma epithelial cells (A549). The innate bioactivity of these natural vesicles was compared to that of artificial vesicles (liposomes) loaded with pirfenidone and quercetin, which were used as positive effector controls in the study. Previous studies have demonstrated that liposomal loading significantly improves the bioavailability, cellular uptake and bioactivity of both pirfenidone and quercetin [17,32,42].

4.1. Oxidative stress

Oxidative stress plays a central role in the progression of chronic airway inflammation and the pathogenesis of inflammatory lung disease [8]. Elevated levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS) are commonly observed in patients with respiratory diseases such as acute lung injury (ALI), idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (IPF), chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and coronavirus disease (COVID-19) [51]. In this inflammatory-microenvironment, excessive oxidative stress inhibits an

Fig. 8. The effects of (A) nanoalgosomes, (B) pirfenidone liposomes, (C) quercetin liposomes and (D) pirfenidone and quercetin co-loaded liposomes on TGF- β 1 expression in A549 cells exposed to the fibrotic agent, $8 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ bleomycin sulphate (fold change relative to negative control). All data are presented as means \pm S. D. ($n = 3$ independent biological samples). Statistical significance compared to the negative control was assessed using the Kruskal-Wallis test with post-hoc pairwise comparisons: ns (not significant) $p > 0.05$, * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$ and *** $p \leq 0.001$.

effective endogenous antioxidant defense [8]. As a solution, exogenous antioxidants can alleviate such oxidant-mediated lung injury by scavenging excess intracellular ROS [26].

Pirfenidone and quercetin have been shown to ameliorate pulmonary inflammation and fibrosis by inhibiting oxidative stress and downregulating the enzymatic pathways responsible for ROS production [39,45]. For nanoalgosomes, Adamo et al. [2] found that EVs from the chlorophyte *Tetraselmis chuii* reduced oxidative stress in human mammary epithelial cells and proinflammatory cytokine release in immune-responsive macrophages. The current study further examined the bioactive properties of nanoalgosomes in A549 lung carcinoma cells, assessing their potential as EV-based effectors in pulmonary pharmacology. In this study, the EVs significantly attenuated intracellular ROS in A549 cells by 2.3-fold compared to bleomycin-exclusive treatments, thereby positively influencing REDOX balance. This intrinsic antioxidant activity of the empty nanoalgosomes was comparable to that of liposomes loaded with the well-established antioxidants pirfenidone and quercetin.

4.2. Transforming growth factor beta-1 and epithelial-mesenchymal transition

Oxidative stress in the airway epithelium induces the activation of proinflammatory cytokines such as transforming growth factor (TGF)- β 1 [6,12]. TGF- β 1 is a key mediator in the pathogenesis of chronic respiratory diseases and lung metastasis [12,28,55,59]. In this study, the treatments (nanoalgosomes and loaded liposomes) significantly downregulated the expression of the TGF- β 1 gene and reduced the accumulation of the TGF- β 1 proprotein compared to the bleomycin-only treatment group. These results ($p \leq 0.05$) suggest that, like the positive control (loaded liposomes), the nanoalgosomes modulate TGF- β 1 expression, potentially influencing EMT-related processes.

Previous studies have shown that pirfenidone reduces the incidence of lung cancer in patients with idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis [33]. Additionally, Marwitz et al. [31] found that pirfenidone inhibited TGF- β pathway activation, leading to reduced tumor growth and size *in vivo*. TGF- β 1 regulates alveolar EMT [43]. In turn, the invasive mesenchymal phenotype is central to the development of a tumor-promoting microenvironment [43]. EMT is characterised by the loss of epithelial markers such as the *CDH1* gene, which encodes the tumor suppressor protein

Fig. 9. The effects of (A) nanoalgosomes, (B) pirfenidone liposomes, (C) quercetin liposomes and (D) pirfenidone and quercetin co-loaded liposomes on *CDH1* expression in A549 cells exposed to the fibrotic agent, $8 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ bleomycin sulphate (fold change relative to negative control). All data are presented as means \pm S. D. ($n = 3$ independent biological samples). Statistical significance compared to the negative control was assessed using the Kruskal-Wallis test with post-hoc pairwise comparisons: ns (not significant) $p > 0.05$, * $p \leq 0.05$ and ** $p \leq 0.01$.

E-cadherin found in the membrane of epithelial cells [34,35]. In the present study, both the nanoalgosomes and loaded liposomes increased the expression of the *CDH1* gene relative to bleomycin-exclusive treatments. These results ($p \leq 0.05$) suggest that the treatments promote epithelial cell integrity and may help prevent EMT progression in response to bleomycin-induced stress. Additionally, there was a decrease in mesenchymal characteristics, including cell migration, elongation and the development of a fusiform spindle-like morphology [36]. However, EMT is not just a simple switch between two states; it involves intermediate or hybrid states where cells exhibit characteristics of both epithelial and mesenchymal phenotypes, contributing to considerable heterogeneity at gene expression level [21,50]. In this context, *VIM* expression, which is associated with mesenchymal cells, was significantly reduced in A549 cells treated with the nanoalgosomes and loaded liposomes relative to bleomycin-exclusive treatments (Appendices Fig. A5). These results ($p \leq 0.05$) suggests that the nanoalgosomes act as effectors in EMT. The EVs may enable the cells to maintain an epithelial state without invasive properties, as evidenced by the increased expression of the epithelial marker *CDH1* and decreased expression of the mesenchymal marker *VIM*, along with reduced

migration compared to the bleomycin-only treatment group ($p \leq 0.01$).

4.3. Fibronectin and glutathione peroxidase 4

Excessive deposition of the extracellular matrix protein fibronectin (FN) is a hallmark of tumour progression, fibrotic conditions, and other pathologies [47,54]. In the pathological microenvironment, FN promotes malignant cell invasion. Recent research has shown that FN facilitates tumor progression in non-small lung cancer cells through the integrin $\alpha\beta3$ /PI3K/AKT/SOX2 signaling pathway [54]. Moreover, pirfenidone and quercetin have been shown to reduce excessive FN deposition in the extracellular matrix by inhibiting the Smad-dependant TGF- β signalling pathway [27,56]. In the present study, both the empty nanoalgosomes and loaded liposomes significantly reduced fibronectin mRNA expression (*FN1*) compared to bleomycin-exclusive treatments ($p \leq 0.05$). Furthermore, the treatments enhanced the expression of glutathione peroxidase 4 (*GPX4*) compared to the bleomycin-only treatment group ($p \leq 0.05$). The antioxidant enzyme GPX4 suppresses ferroptosis (i.e., cell death caused by iron-dependant lipid peroxidation) [11]. Bleomycin treatments have been shown to downregulate GPX4 in

Fig. 10. The effects of the treatments (nanoalgosomes and loaded liposomes) on (A) *FNI* and *GPX4* expression and (B) TGF- β 1 production in A549 cells exposed to the fibrotic agent, 8 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ bleomycin sulphate (fold change relative to negative control). Treatments were 4 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for nanoalgosomes, 1 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for quercetin liposomes, 4 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for pirfenidone liposomes and 4 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ pirfenidone for pirfenidone and quercetin co-loaded liposomes (1.00:0.06 pirfenidone:quercetin ratio). Concentrations were selected based on the dose-response data from previous analyses, optimized to ensure minimal toxicity while achieving the desired biological effects. All data are presented as means \pm S.D. ($n = 3$ independent biological samples). Statistical significance compared to the negative control was assessed using the Kruskal-Wallis test with post-hoc pairwise comparisons: ns (not significant) $p > 0.05$, * $p \leq 0.05$ and *** $p \leq 0.001$.

lung tissue homogenates [58]. *GPX4* is also involved in EMT and the regulation of the invasive mesenchymal phenotype [37]. For instance, depletion of *GPX4* accelerates tumor progression by promoting the infiltration of tumor-associated macrophages [11]. *GPX4* also modulates TGF- β -induced myofibroblast differentiation by regulating ROS and Smad signaling in lung fibroblasts [49]. Thus, the upregulation of *GPX4* observed in the present study may contribute to the attenuation of intracellular ROS by both the nanoalgosomes and liposomal nano-carriers in the bleomycin-stressed model. The results suggest that the treatments may help attenuate EMT by downregulating fibronectin and TGF- β 1, while simultaneously promoting antioxidant activity through the upregulation of *GPX4*, potentially mitigating bleomycin-induced cellular stress.

4.4. Co-loaded pirfenidone and quercetin liposomes

Although the co-loaded liposomes containing pirfenidone and quercetin were hypothesised to exhibit synergistic effects, the results did not demonstrate a clear enhancement in EMT attenuation compared to the single-drug formulations. Importantly, synergism and antagonism in drug combinations can occur in a concentration-dependent manner [7].

In the present study, the 1.00:0.06 pirfenidone to quercetin ratio in the co-loaded formulation may not have been optimal for synergistic interaction, potentially leading to suboptimal effects. It is possible that the concentration of quercetin in this ratio was too low to elicit a significant additive or synergistic effect, or it may have resulted in antagonistic interactions that offset the potential benefits of the combination. Utilising a dose matrix, rather than a single-dose combination, could help identify the most effective dosing combination, thereby enhancing confidence in the findings of synergism or antagonism for this dual combination [7]. Furthermore, the lack of observed synergistic effects between pirfenidone and quercetin may be attributed to the potential overlap in their mechanisms of action, reducing their individual efficacy. Both pirfenidone and quercetin reduce oxidative stress, inhibit TGF- β 1 signaling, and regulate fibrosis-related markers such as *FNI* and *GPX4*. This shared mechanism of action may have led to a saturation effect, where the effects of each compound were not enhanced upon combination, as they could have been partially acting through overlapping or similar activation pathways.

5. Conclusions

In this study, the innate bioactivity of nanoalgsomes was compared to liposomes loaded with the established therapeutics (pirfenidone and quercetin) in a bleomycin-stressed A549 cell model. Both the nanoalgsomes and the loaded liposomal nanocarriers ($1\text{--}4\ \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) attenuated bleomycin-induced EMT, inhibited cell migration, suppressed the profibrotic marker TGF- β 1, downregulated intracellular ROS, and enhanced *GPX4* expression. Notably, the innate bioactivity of the nanoalgsomes was comparable to that of the loaded liposomal nanocarriers in counteracting bleomycin-induced stress in A549 cells. The bioactive properties of nanoalgsomes, including their ability to modulate oxidative stress and fibrosis-related pathways, could hold significant potential for the development of next-generation, naturally derived nanoformulations for treating respiratory diseases and cancer.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Touzet Nicolas: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Schaaf Maximilian:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation. **Mateos-Maroto Ana:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Picciozzo Sabrina:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Morsbach Svenja:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology. **Adamo Giorgia:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Si Shutian:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Lieberwirth Ingo:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Rose-nauer Christine:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Landfester Katharina:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Bongiovanni Antonella:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Conlon Thomas:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors AB and NT declare the following financial competing interests: AB and NT have filed the patent (PCT/EP2020/086622) related to microalgal-derived extracellular vesicles (nanoalgsomes) described in the paper. AB and NT are co-founders and AB CEO of EVEBiofactory s.r.l. The remaining authors declare no competing interests.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT in order to improve language and readability. After using this tool, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.biopha.2025.118081](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2025.118081).

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

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